

CIVIL SOCIETY INSTITUTIONS' PARTICIPATION IN ELECTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN PRACTICE

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Elections for representative bodies of state power hold significant importance for all civil society institutions within the country. This importance stems from the fact that these institutions' interests are reflected in the reforms enacted by the political entity that assumes power post-election. We posit that open, transparent elections, coupled with the active involvement of voters and civil society institutions in endorsing deserving candidates, will yield positive outcomes.

To effectively evaluate the involvement of civil society institutions in elections, it is crucial to first define these institutions. This includes identifying their specific scope, types, and the nature of their activities. Currently, the lack of a clear definition of civil society institutions in existing legal regulations hampers the precise assessment of their participation, activity, and performance in elections.

In our republic, the election process has seen active participation primarily from self-governing bodies, mass media, and political parties, which are all part of civil society institutions. However, assessing the involvement of other civil society institutions in elections presents a unique challenge. This is largely due to the absence of their precise definitions in the regulatory documents.

The active involvement of civil society institutions in ensuring transparent and open elections is crucial. In a specific survey conducted as part of our research, we asked, "Do you believe the participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations in elections is adequate?"

Here are the results:

- **20.1%** of respondents felt that while the law empowers these organizations, it is not effectively enforced.
- **8.9%** believed that their participation is restricted.
- **28.1%** found it difficult to provide an answer.

In summary, **57.1%** of respondents did not deem the participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations in elections to be sufficient. This indicates that citizens are not well-acquainted with the operations of these

organizations. They struggle to accurately evaluate their resources, capabilities, and effectiveness. Furthermore, they are not adequately informed about the activities of these organizations, especially their involvement in election processes.

One of the pressing tasks is to enhance the involvement of civil society institutions in election processes. This should be done considering their influence, resources, and capabilities, as they play a significant role in public oversight during the preparation and execution of elections.

It is recognized that observers from foreign nations and esteemed international organizations provide reports on our republic's election outcomes. Specifically, the report by international observers on the 2019 elections to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan and local councils highlighted a problem concerning the participation of civil society institutions in elections. The election code does stipulate that a public observer oversees the election process. However, this status is exclusively granted to observers from "Mahalla" committees, which are citizen self-governing bodies that participate in various stages of the election process. This limitation could be a potential area for improvement in future elections¹.

As a part of civil society institutions, the neighborhood institute plays a crucial role in election processes. It assists in defining the boundaries of polling stations, compiling and verifying the voter list, and organizing pre-election promotional activities. This involvement further emphasizes the importance of civil society institutions in ensuring a fair and transparent electoral process.

The diverse roles played by civil society institutions, such as the neighborhood institute, could potentially influence their ability to act as impartial observers, leading to a conflict of interests. For instance, discrepancies can be observed in pre-election campaigns, the organization of meetings between candidates and voters, and efforts to engage voters in these meetings. This highlights the need for clear guidelines and regulations to ensure the impartiality of these institutions during elections.

This complex situation has been observed by foreign observers as well. We believe that the participation of citizen self-governing bodies in the organizational aspects of the election campaign can compromise their role as independent observers. This is because the organizational responsibilities

¹ "Parliamentary Elections of the Republic of Uzbekistan, December 22, 2019." Final Report of the Election Observation Mission of the OSCE ODIHR. Warsaw, May 13, 2020. P.-4.

during the campaign, particularly on voting day, demand significant resources and efforts from the entities in charge. Therefore, it seems prudent to reduce the involvement of citizen self-governing bodies in the organizational aspects of the election campaign to preserve their impartiality. This adjustment could help ensure a more transparent and fair election process.

One of the key roles of civil society institutions in elections is their participation as observers. Elections are conducted not just in urban areas, but across the entire republic, including remote regions. However, the fact that civil society institutions are primarily based in cities and conduct most of their activities there presents a challenge. Their involvement in electoral processes in rural areas often incurs additional costs, which complicates their ability to participate as observers in these regions. This highlights the need for strategies to facilitate their involvement in rural areas, ensuring comprehensive observation and participation across all regions.

The OSCE ODIHR mission, which observed our country's presidential election campaign from September to December 2016, highlighted a lack of diversity in the programs of political parties and a deficiency in competition among them². The state financing system for political parties was identified as a factor negatively impacting their independent operation. This observation underscores the need for reforms to encourage diversity and independence among political parties, thereby fostering a more dynamic and representative political landscape.

It's worth noting that the state and government do pay considerable attention to civil society institutions, particularly political parties, during the election campaign. The campaign period is known to be the most active time for direct communication between political parties and citizens, who are the voters. Concurrently, voters are keen on understanding the tangible results achieved by the political parties. They express this interest during meetings with representatives and candidates of the political parties, often posing questions in this context. This underscores the importance of transparency and accountability in the political process.

The Election Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan outlines the powers of the Central Election Commission. It states that the Commission can engage in international cooperation with election bodies of other countries, international organizations, and foreign representatives. This includes organizing meetings, establishing agreements and memoranda, and inviting these entities to observe

² Bulletin of the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2017, No. 1-2, P.-725.

the elections. However, it's noteworthy that the Code does not provide for social cooperation with local non-governmental non-profit organizations in these areas. This could be an area for potential amendment to ensure broader participation and oversight in the electoral process.

The mandate of the Central Election Commission, as defined in the Election Code, is focused on "strengthening and developing relations with the public and the mass media". However, this mandate is somewhat limited in scope. While it necessitates the establishment of effective cooperation with non-governmental and non-profit organizations, including signing memorandums with them, it does not extend to inviting representatives of these organizations to observe the elections. This could be an area for potential expansion to ensure a more inclusive and transparent electoral process.

The limited active participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations in elections is closely tied to the lack of attention given to their involvement by the Central Election Commission and other state agencies. As previously mentioned, a key issue is the absence of a developed legal framework that supports and regulates their participation. This highlights the need for legal reforms to foster a more inclusive and representative electoral process.

During the research, it was observed that the cooperation memoranda signed between political parties and other civil society institutions highlight several important issues. For instance, while these memoranda often provide for cooperation in certain activities, their implementation in practice, particularly in ensuring an effective and transparent election process, is not always sufficient. This underscores the need for more robust enforcement of these memoranda to ensure their objectives are fully realized in practice. This could contribute to a more inclusive and transparent electoral process.

The issues highlighted indicate that the legal norms pertaining to the participation of non-governmental non-profit organizations in elections are not adequately incorporated into the electoral legislation. Furthermore, the norms that aim to encourage the activity of these organizations in elections are insufficient. This underscores the need for comprehensive legal reforms to ensure a more inclusive and representative electoral process. These reforms could potentially enhance the democratic nature of elections by ensuring broader participation and representation.

In conclusion, elections to representative bodies of state power hold significant importance for all civil society institutions within the country. This is because their interests are reflected in the reforms enacted by the political

entity that assumes power post-election. Given this, one of the pressing tasks is to monitor and train personnel working in non-governmental non-profit organizations. This could enhance their effectiveness and participation in the electoral process, thereby fostering a more inclusive and representative political landscape.

Indeed, while voluntary participation of citizens in non-governmental non-profit organizations during election processes is important, it is not sufficient. Active engagement, continuous education, and effective communication strategies are also crucial to ensure these organizations can effectively represent the interests of the citizens and contribute to a fair and transparent electoral process. This highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to enhance the role of non-governmental non-profit organizations in elections.

In addition to the issues previously discussed, several other factors play a crucial role in ensuring the active participation of civil society institutions. These include the independence of the media, the development of an informed and digitally savvy society, and the growth of self-governing media institutions. Addressing these issues positively can significantly enhance the election processes. This underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach to foster a more inclusive and representative political landscape.

References:

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2. National Database of Legislative Information. 25.06.2019, 03/19/544/3337.
3. Bulletin of the Central Election Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2017, No. 1-2, P.-125.